

Peptidyl-prolyl cis/trans isomerase (PPI) activation in homeostasis loss.

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Major determinants for loss in homeostasis in the cell include events that impair or interfere with protein folding of specific polypeptides or globally across the proteome. We integrated systems biologic cellular analysis across cell type and stimulus to identify major components of the homeostasis gene signature in human cells. We identify here members of the peptidyl prolyl isomerase (PPI) gene family including *PPIA* and *PPIF* major effectors of the cellular homeostasis program. In human cells with ectopic expression of *PPIA*, also known as Cyclophilin A, we found resultant loss of expression in the metallothionein stress response gene *MT2A*, supporting a direct role for the PPI/Cyclophilin family in cellular homeostasis.

Citation

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